

FREQUENCY NORMALIZATION OF SOLAR PV- THERMAL ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEM BY USING ANFIS CONTROLLERS

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ABSTRACT

Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology has developed rapidly and diversified in recent years. The growth can be attributed predominantly to the sustainability and reliability of energy sources. The solar photovoltaic (PV) thermal electric plant consists of several interconnected units. In a consequence of this, there is a potential of non-linearity in frequency as well as the system parameters of the storage system's reasoning both internal and external load parameters. In order to achieve the finest conceivable results in terms of effectiveness, accuracy, and adaptability, a diverse set of LFC have been designed and proposed. A wide range of significant AI techniques, like fuzzy logic and the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) based frequency controller models, have been identified over the recent developments. This paper present various ANFIS based progressive controller designs in the recent decade.

Keywords: Solar Photovoltaic, Thermal electric system, Fuzzy logic controller, Frequency controller, Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS).

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar photovoltaic (PV) generation is becoming increasingly popular as an alternate source of energy to help make up for the increasing energy gap. Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology is both ecologically responsible and sustainable. The Weather-induced instability in the power output of PV systems has a bigger impact on the electrical grid since the total capacity of PV solar energy systems installed around the world is expected to rise by more than tenfold in the next decade. The regulation of the electric grid's voltage and frequency could be adversely affected. It is widely acknowledged that solar photovoltaic thermal power plants play a crucial role in the transformation of conventional to renewable energy generation. Because of the intermittent nature of PV generation systems, their integration into electrical grids creates system frequency difficulties. Solar power generation is recommended as an alternate power source due to the huge availability of solar radiation, despite the difficulties provided by the solar power production and power system integration.

The widespread integration of the small-scale PV generation systems and distributed systems into the energy grid requires a better understanding about the variable nature of the solar power supplied by a single device or a group of such devices. Hybrid systems, which include a power infrastructure that makes use of renewable energy, are crucial for these reasons. There has been a worldwide rise in the use of distributed photovoltaic power generation. Increased output efficiency, reduced cost of photovoltaic modules, and governmental incentives have all contributed to this development. PV power, on the other hand, varies according to the climatic conditions, the season of year, and the geographic location of the installation, which can lead to issues in the operation of an electric power system such as voltage fluctuations and large frequency deviations.(Datta 2014). In such cases, necessity of frequency controller devices is demanding. This article discusses the concepts of frequency normalization and control in solar PV thermal power systems. The contextual analysis is structured and briefed from the fundamental point followed by reported frequency normalization approaches and extended to the proposed significant research on ANFIS based frequency controllers with efficient performances.

Fig.01 ANFIS-based frequency controllers [1]

2. SOLAR PV-THERMAL ELECTRIC POWER SYSTEMS

Solar thermal power/electric generation plants are systems that capture and focus sunlight to generate the high-temperature heat required to produce electricity.

Fig.02 General concept of solar thermal conversion system

Credit: Mark Fedkin (modified after Duffie and Beckman, 2013)

In the vast majority of setups, the steaming process begins with the heating and subsequent circulation of a heat-transfer fluid within in the receiver. Steam is passed through a turbine, where its heat is turned into mechanical energy. This energy is then used to turn a generator and produce electricity. Tracking systems are incorporated into solar thermal power systems, and its objective is to direct the sunlight effectively onto the receiver regardless of the position of the sun during the day. Additionally, the micro grid is coupled with solar photovoltaic and solar thermal power plants to accommodate load requirements.

In consequence to deviations in frequency of the load input, concerns connected to the intrinsic intermittency of PV power output would increase. These include estimating a PV system's yield, optimised energy storage, balancing generation and load, and supporting power quality. Solar power variability is predominantly caused by heterogeneity caused by weather- in down welling the solar radiation, hence the studies based on the data and the quantifications of the variability in irradiance are vital to a stable operation and successful design of the future power grids. The output of a solar system and the configuration of its energy storage are mostly impacted by irradiance variability, whereas power quality and generation load balance are impacted by increment variability (Lohmann 2018).

3. FREQUENCY NORMALISATION

When it comes to modern electronics, having a reliable source of electricity is essential, and frequency robustness is a key component in attaining a minimum standard. Classical controllers can't reduce frequency resonances. Recently, Load Frequency Control (LFC) controllers have been developed and implemented to improve power system frequency resiliency. Different design solutions have been implemented by researchers for maintaining tie line power and regulated system frequency. The controllable, self-sufficient generation based

on solar PV can be conceived as a single area. The AC tie-line connects this control zone to thermal generation control regions (Akbar Karimipouya 2019).

Fig.03 Frequency Normalisation (Source: expertmind.com)

It ensures that electricity requirements are satisfied, and network load frequency is consistent. Considering the load duration curve shifts during the day, it is necessary to equip generators solar PV with frequency regulators. Two-step frequency control improves stability. Due to the imbalance between the power supplied and power required, the principal control movement uses droop control to alleviate the imbalance. The former adjusts the frequency at which the generators of control region, tracks the load variations and share it proportionally within 20 second process. The latter fine-tunes the frequency by resetting the error to zero. Adjusting the reference set point of load modifies the speed-load relationship (Mendel 1995). Through the AC tie line, which connects the various substations, it is possible to transfer power between different substations.

The regulation of both voltage and primary frequency is an essential variable for the functioning of energy industry. In the event that the grid supplies a lower voltage than usual, the production can become unbalanced. In a similar vein, a favourable environment exists when there is an increased supply. To overcome the restrictions of conventional frequency controllers and achieve frequency normalisation, some researchers, resorted to (AI) artificial intelligence methods like fuzzy logic (FL). Fuzzy controllers are effective for the resolution of a wide variety of control issues as a result of their robustness and reliability. The application of fuzzy logic can be seen in a few different real-world scenarios. Controlling systems like warm water, robots, heat exchangers, the electricity system, and nuclear reactors are all employed with FL. In order to generate the required outcome, a fuzzy logic system will normally consist of a rule base, fuzzifier, de-fuzzifier and inference engines.

4. ANFIS CONTROLLERS FOR FREQUENCY NORMALIZATION

Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) Controllers

ANFIS is a kind of artificial neural network that is based on the Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy inference system. It combines the learning capabilities of neural networks with fuzzy logic to map an input space to an output space. This system can learn the behaviour of a complex system and is often used in control applications where the precise model of the system is not known.

In the context of a Solar PV-Thermal Electric Power System, an ANFIS controller can be used to stabilize the power supply by adjusting control parameters in response to frequency variations. The controller detects frequency changes which could be due to fluctuations in solar irradiance, changes in load demand, or other factors. Then, it adjusts the control parameters to ensure that the frequency is normalized and the power supply remains stable.

4.1 FLC: Fuzzy Logic controllers (FLC) can be used in many different ways with renewable energy sources. Since FLC is feasible method to employ, its popularity has grown over the past 10 years. FLC also handles inputs that aren't accurate, that further means the controller doesn't need a precise mathematical model (Rituraj et al. 2022). This method is a modification of conventional logic rules. Within the context of this, the degree of

truth that can range anywhere from 0.0 to 1.0. The standard logic works only for ideas that are 100% true or 100% false. Whereas, fuzzy logic uses concepts to figure out how to reason about things that are inherently hard to comprehend.

Area control error (ACE) and Integral of area control error (IACE) can be used to construct a nonlinear proportional-integral (PI) Fuzzy Logic Controller. Negative Small (NS), the Negative Big (NB), the Zero Error (ZE), the Positive Small (PS), and the Positive Big (PB) comprises of ACE and IACE with triangular, symmetrical membership function. PB, PS, ZE, NS and NB are the fuzzified output zones in the controller. For an input of two sets, the ACE and the integration of ACE, 25 possible rule sets are generated in order to achieve PV-Thermal system action. The suggested Frequency Gain Scheduling (FGS) controllers by Cam et. Al., (Kocaarslan and Çam 2005) outperform optimum and conventional controllers. The work was further expanded for a two-area restructured reheat thermal power system to demonstrate the suggested approach's ability to handle restructured power systems. The results showed that the control technique which was proposed is robust, economical, simple, direct and effective, to implement with better dynamic quality and dependability compared to conventional PI controllers (Kumar 2016). Alam et al., (Alam, Azeem, and Alouani 2014) reported optimal FLC performance for fixed and variable load situations, delivering constant output voltage and harness able maximum output power. Also, the research comprehended that FLC interpolates among the rules and consequences based on firing strength using heuristic knowledge and equivalent to several PID/PI controllers with smooth interpolation for real-time applications.

4.2 ANFIS: The ANFIS, Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System, is defined as a system which models input as well as the output data through a training process. As a result of this action, system is able to adjust its parameters for determining the relation that exists between the input data and the output data. The capacity of neuro-fuzzy systems to solicit interpretable IF-THEN rules is arguably their greatest strength.

The power of neuro-fuzzy systems lies in their ability to satisfy two seemingly incompatible goals in fuzzy modelling: interpretability and accuracy. In actual use, either of the two features will predominate over the other. Research subjected to the field of neuro-fuzzy modelling can be categorized into two groups: linguistic fuzzy modelling, which has an emphasis on interpretability, and precise fuzzy modelling, which focuses on accuracy. The usage of ANFIS has several benefits, such as the fact that it is concise and uncomplicated to implement in comparison to the other basic approaches, and it also reduces the amount of time needed for the programme to execute.

Naglaa K. Bahgaat et al. (2014) designed the algorithm of ANFIS for which initially the basic rule for the controller is simulated and the training data is included with two inputs ACE and IACE which encloses the plant behavior for different load perturbations. Further the function “anfisedit” is employed to create .fis file and the training data is loaded to generate FIS structure with suitable membership function. The data is trained with certain number of epochs. Two major mathematical models are categorized for best efficiency. The output of the model y is nonlinear with respect to the input variable represented as (X) , is shown in the following equation (Jood, Aggarwal, and Chopra 2019; Moyo, Tabakov, and Moyo 2021):

$$y = f(X) + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where, y represents the PI controller output. X represents input variable vector, consisting of ACE with its derivative ($\frac{d}{dt}ACE$) as the inputs and ϵ represents the error term. The other method is Takagi-Sugeno-Kang model, which is described as in (Mazinan and Kazemi 2010),

$$z_i = p_i x + q_i y + r_i \quad (2)$$

where x_i , y_i represents the inputs variables to the ANFIS, the antecedent membership functions of each input are considered later as A_i and B_i , z_i represents the output, the p_i and q_i represents weighting factors for the i^{th} input, and r_i represents i^{th} output bias. The results of the simulations show that the frequency of the grids may be efficiently regulated by employing the proposed control approach, despite the elimination of energy storage equipment, significant changes to the system parameters, and the possibility of a modelling defect. Series controllers used accomplishes stable frequency regulation in the presence of noise and varying input parameters. The results of the comparison between tie line power deviations and the percentage of frequency reduction depicts that ANFIS controller is able to hold a more robust performance in comparison to ANN, RCGA and HCPSO controllers by minimizing steady state deviations with respect to the overshoot settling time and undershoot (Mahboob et al. 2022).

4.3 Optimized ANFIS models: Accomplishments were reported to improve the effectiveness and functionality of the ANFIS algorithm. Solar photovoltaic (PV) thermal systems typically have a layout with

multiple points of connection. The potential for frequency instability in the system as a whole grows as its surface area expands. In order to reduce the control time and decrease the frequency changes during the power systems with active operation, these authors proposed a modern algorithm for optimization, an antlion optimizer (ALO) for the training of ANFIS methodology LFC which are incorporated in the multi-interconnected plants. The results obtained validated the effectiveness of proposed ALO-ANFIS controller in determining the optimal gains for interconnected power systems (Fathy and Kassem 2019).

In a deregulated scenario, an ANFIS controller tuned by an (ACS), artificial cooperative search algorithm is proposed for optimal gain tuning of an LFC. The ACS algorithm was designed as a swarm intelligence approach to resolving numerical optimization issues. Swarm intelligence is the foundation of the ACS algorithm, which performs by having two artificial superorganisms migrate and interact biologically inspired behaviour to find the global minimum value for the specific problem. This projected algorithm tuned by ANFIS is implemented on a two area and two unit interconnected deregulated power system to depict its robustness and competence (Kumar Selvaraju et al. 2017). While an ACS-tuned controller requires more time for execution, an ANFIS controller responds rapidly to changes in operating conditions. The online LFC operation in a deregulated scenario is best served by the ANFIS controller tuned by ACS algorithm (Rajamand 2021).

The reports (Baghya Shree and Kamaraj 2016) confirmed that Artificial neural network (ANN) have various power engineering applications due to their ability to synthesise multidimensional and perceptible planning, robustness, fault forbearance and briskness due to parallel mechanism. Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) is used for the automatic generation control of three unequal area in Solar PV-Thermal systems. The ANN controller employs back propagation method, which is a method based on iterations using the gradient standard algorithm to minimise the min. square error for each training pattern. It initiates from output layer and proceeds backwards to the first hidden layer to update the network weights.

Surya Prakash et. Al.,(Prakash and Sinha 2018) worked on examining a load control in an interconnected grid built on microgrid based on the fleet of EVs (Electric Vehicles) and solar PV system which are integrated with area-1 (thermal power plant). Incorporating sliding surfaces frequency controllers with modified ANFIS algorithm approach improves performance by decreasing oscillation in tie-line power and frequency in each location. Two additional devices the Thyristor Control Phase Shifter (TCPS) and the Ultra-Capacitor (UC) are on a large hybrid linked power system frequency stability. Different instances examine small and substantial load changes. The ANFIS system was structured with the same components as a typical fuzzy system but conceals semantic features of the underlying fuzzy system.

4.4 ANFIS results and discussion: The accuracy of an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) model can be evaluated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2), which are calculated using equations (1) and (2). Additionally, Equation (3) can be employed to compute the percentage mean relative error [20].

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{x=1}^N (a_x - p_x)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum_{x=1}^N (a_x - p_x)^2}{\sum_{x=1}^N (a_x - a_x^{\wedge})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$MRE(\%) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{x=1}^N \left[100 \frac{|a_x - p_x|}{a_x} \right] \quad (3)$$

In the given context, ' a_x ' represents the actual value, ' p_x ' signifies the predicted value, ' a_x ' denotes the mean of experimental values, and 'N' represents the total number of experiments.

4.5 ANFIS Analysis: This research involved the creation of three separate Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) models. These models were designed to assess both the thermal and electrical efficiencies of a water-based Photovoltaic/Thermal (PV/T) system, alongside a model dedicated to evaluating the electrical efficiency of a standard Photovoltaic (PV) system. For enhanced verification, a comparative analysis of the results from each model was conducted, as detailed in Table 1. The study concluded that the ANFIS models using exponentially transformed data provided more accurate predictions of PV/T system performance, as evidenced by lower RMSE values, compared to the models using raw data [21].

Error performance Metrics	Thermal efficiency (ANFIS Model 1)	Electrical efficiency (PV/T) (ANFIS Model 2)	Electrical efficiency (PV) (ANFIS Model 3)
MSE	36.5176	0.0440	0.0021
RMSE	6.0430	0.2097	0.0089
MAE	0.2243	0.0197	0.0459
R ²	0.6876	0.9920	0.9994

Table 1: Results regarding the performance parameters of the ANFIS model [21].

Fig. 8 illustrates the 3D surface ANFIS output, with (a) showcasing the thermal efficiency (%) in relation to radiation and power, and (b) displaying the electrical efficiency (%) concerning power and radiation [21].

As depicted in Figure 8, the ANFIS model outputs indicate that the electrical efficiency of PV systems decreases with an increase in the surface temperature of the PV panel. Conversely, there is a noticeable increase in electrical efficiency when the surface temperature of the PV module decreases due to cooling effects at the rear side of the PV/T system. The ANFIS models also reveal a linear relationship between power and thermal efficiency; as output power increases, thermal efficiency increases accordingly, as illustrated in Figure 8(a). Furthermore, Figure 8(b) demonstrates an inverse correlation between radiation and electrical efficiency. A decrease in solar radiation leads to an enhancement in electrical efficiency. This suggests that high solar radiation intensity during the day can elevate the surface temperature of the PV module, consequently reducing electrical output efficiency. Therefore, implementing a cooling fluid system at the rear side of the PV module to absorb excess heat can significantly enhance electrical efficiency compared to systems without such cooling mechanisms.

Conclusion

By incorporating ANFIS-based frequency controllers into a power system, possibility to enhance the system's degree of adaptability is augmented. It is clear from the analysis of the reports that ANFIS-based controllers have coherent and productive perpetual output. When compared to the traditional PI frequency controllers or the elemental fuzzy controller performances, the two-step arrangement ensures more reliable linear productivity. This contextual examination has motivated for future novel idea for employing Swarm optimization techniques based ANFIS controllers. These techniques propose high energy parameters to lead sustainable operations regardless of any system. The training data applied through ACE and Integrated ACE as inputs will be regulated to normalize the frequency deviations in the system.

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